

PBTK-TD model of the phagocytosis activity in three-spined stickleback exposed to BPA

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Abstract

Due to the high production volume and persistence in the environment of bisphenol A (BPA) and its substitutes, realistic exposure scenarii were proposed in some species to better understand the relationship between external and internal concentrations. For example, a recent PBTK model has been developed and adapted to BPA ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolization, and Excretion) processes in three-spined stickleback. These substances have an impact on organism physiology including reproductive and immune functions. In this context, physiologically-based toxicokinetic models coupled with toxicodynamics (PBTK-TD) have proven to be valuable tools to fill the knowledge gap between external exposure and effect dynamics. The aim of the current work was to explain the impact of BPA on the immune response by determining its temporality. In addition, the relationship between BPA dose and these responses was investigated using a PBTK-TD model. Two experiments were performed on stickleback to characterize their biomarker responses, (i) a short exposure (14 days) at 0, 10 and 100 µg/L, including a depuration phase (7 days), and (ii) a long exposure (21 days) at 100 µg/L to measure the immunomarker dynamic over a long period. The fish spleens were sampled to analyze immune responses of stickleback at various times of exposure and depuration: leucocyte distribution, phagocytic capacity and efficiency, lysosomal presence and leucocyte respiratory burst index. At the same date, blood, muscle, and liver were sampled to quantify BPA and their metabolites (BPA monoglucuronide and BPA monosulfate). All these data enabled the development of the indirect pharmacodynamic models (PBTK-TD) by implementing the responses of biomarkers in the existing BPA PBTK of stickleback. The results shown a high induction of phagocytosis activity by BPA in the two exposure conditions. Furthermore, the immunomarkers exhibit very different temporal dynamics. This study demonstrates the need of a thorough characterization of biomarker response for a further use in Environmental Biomonitoring.

Keywords : PBTK-TD model, immunomarker, phagocytosis, fish, BPA, three-spined stickleback.

36 **1. Introduction**

37 Bisphenol A (BPA) is one of the most used and studied endocrine-disrupting compounds (EDCs)
38 worldwide (Faheem and Bhandari, 2021). In 2015, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)
39 evaluated the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) of BPA to be equal to 4000 ng/kg body weight and more
40 recently, the European Commission classified this chemical as a substance of very high concern (SVHC)
41 (Ougier et al., 2021).

42 In response to the concerns regarding adverse outcomes that could result from daily exposure to BPA
43 and stricter legislation, industries have started to replace BPA with various structural analogs (Oliviero
44 et al., 2022). Nevertheless, production volume of BPA remains high (Faheem and Bhandari, 2021;
45 Samuel et al., 2022). Accidental direct or indirect release from wastewater treatment or the natural
46 deterioration of products containing BPA leads to its ubiquity in aquatic ecosystems. Most aquatic
47 organisms are usually exposed to less than 1 µg/L, but waters near industrialized sites could lead to
48 exposures of hundreds of µg/L (Flint et al., 2012). Thus, the continuous exposure of aquatic communities
49 to BPA has been of great concern as highlighted by several publications describing its effects on the
50 aquatic organisms.

51 As an EDC, the mode of action of BPA is based on its affinity with hormone receptors (estrogen
52 receptors α and β) but BPA also acts as an antagonist of androgenic receptors and a disruptor of thyroid
53 signaling (Faheem and Bhandari, 2021). It leads to the disruption of reproduction and growth processes
54 in fish, which are extensively described in the literature (Crain et al., 2007; Faheem and Bhandari, 2021).

55 At the end of 2021, EFSA published a new proposal of TDI at 0.04 ng/kg body weight/day (EFSA,
56 2022) one hundred-thousand times lower than the TDI proposed in 2015. This new value was based on
57 *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies in rat that concluded in immunotoxicity of BPA. Thus, exposure to this
58 compound induced parameters involved in inflammatory reactions at various sites, including lungs and
59 epididymis (EFSA, 2022). This recent update of the TDI by EFSA illustrates the understanding that
60 EDC's adverse effects can be perceptible on biological parameters which are not directly related to
61 reproduction. However, despite the close relationship existing between hormones and the immune
62 system in fish, endocrine disruption effects of estrogenic compounds on the immune system are still
63 poorly understood (Harris and Bird, 2000; Milla et al., 2011). Exposure to BPA results in complex
64 immuno-modulatory effects in fish (Michałowicz, 2014). As in mammals, BPA could trigger
65 inflammation by inducing pro-inflammatory markers like cytokines, chemokines and interleukins in
66 zebrafish (Yang et al., 2015). However, at higher dose levels, exposure to BPA could lead to cell
67 apoptosis and death. In addition to this complex relationship regarding the dose, a lack of interest
68 concerning the temporal dynamic of immune markers was noticed in the literature. In general, most *in*
69 *vitro* studies focus on the establishment of dose-response, *e.g.* in Yang et al. (2015), seven different
70 doses of BPA were tested whereas immune parameters were only measured after 6h of exposure. Thus,

71 further investigations need to be performed to better understand the dynamics of immunomarkers over
72 time and for various doses.

73 Biologically based mechanistic models can be used to predict and understand biomarker responses
74 (Forbes et al., 2006). Indeed, traditional dose-response relationships are generally dependent on
75 exposure time and route whereas mechanism-based approaches can be used to extrapolate to other
76 exposure scenarios. In this context, a PBTK-TD model was specifically designed to describe both
77 kinetics and immunomarker responses resulting from exposure to BPA. A PBTK model describing the
78 ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolization and Excretion) processes of BPA in fish has been
79 previously developed (Mit et al., 2022). Notably, this model accurately predicted BPA and BPA
80 metabolites levels in three-spined stickleback organs. An additional toxicodynamic (TD) component,
81 that simulates the effects triggered by a substance or a mixture, was shown to provide better
82 understanding of the toxicity mechanisms by testing hypotheses and, thus, to be potentially relevant for
83 environmental risk assessment (Ling et al., 2005; Mit et al., 2021; Tebby et al., 2019). Thus, modelling
84 responses of immunomarkers in a PBTK-TD model could help understand the relationship between the
85 internal dose and the effect, identify the substance (parent or metabolites) responsible for the response
86 and help characterizing its dynamics. This modelling approach would inform both the temporality of the
87 response, and dose-responses relationships at a given time.

88 The aim of this study was to propose a PBTK with TD sub-models describing immunomarker dynamic
89 responses. TD data were obtained from two exposures to BPA performed on fish in laboratory. An
90 analysis of the immunomarkers was completed prior to their selection and the application of the
91 appropriate TD models. Indirect response models were compared to test hypotheses regarding dose-
92 dependency and the non-trivial temporal dynamics of biomarker modulation.

93 2. Materials and methods

94 The PBTK model in which immune responses are integrated was reported previously in Mit et al., 2022
95 where full details of the experimental approach and model development can be found. Immune
96 responses from spleen samples from the same fish previously exposed to BPA are evaluated here to
97 build on previous work and to gain insight into how BPA and its metabolites affect immunity in fish.
98 An additional experimental dataset is added in the current paper and further denominated as “long
99 exposure”.

100 2.1. Stickleback experimental data

101 Experimental protocols were conducted following the European directive 2010/63/UE for the protection
102 of animals used for scientific purposes at INERIS, registration number E60-769-02. The experimental
103 protocols were submitted and reviewed by a French nationally recognized ethical committee,
104 CREMEAPS, registration number 96. Two experiments were performed, (i) a short exposure (14 days)
105 at two different concentration levels including a depuration phase (7 days), and (ii) a long-exposure (21
106 days) at one concentration level to measure the immunomarker dynamics over a long period (Table 1).
107 In the first experiment (i), internal concentrations and immune responses were measured in three spined
108 stickleback, while in the second (ii), only the immune response was measured. Prior to each experiment,
109 fish sex was determined using a mathematical model which distinguish male from female based on their
110 head morphology (de Kermoysan et al., 2013). Mature fish sexually inactive (found in the field outside
111 the breeding season) were selected to avoid confounding effects that could be introduced by sexual
112 competition between males or females.

Table 1. Description of the two experiments on threespined stickleback

Exposure	Models (biological matrix)	BPA nominal concentration in water ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Experimental Schedule (day)	Metabolites	Fish parameters
Short	TK (Liver, blood, carcasse)	0, 10,100	7d uptake 7d depuration	BPA glu BPA sulf	n = 380
	TD (spleen)				48.8 ± 4.4 mm 1.7 ± 0.4 g
Long	TD (spleen)	0, 100	21d uptake	na	n = 140 52.9 ± 5.9 mm 1.8 ± 0.6 g

113 2.1.1. Short-exposure experiment (14 day)

114 This experiment was previously described in details in Mit et al. (2022). This experiment consisted of
115 seven days of exposure to BPA and seven days of depuration (fish in clear water). Shortly, adult (i.e.
116 mature gonads) but sexually inactive sticklebacks with the same life history (similar age, $n = 380$,

117 48.8 ± 4.4 mm; 1.7 ± 0.4 g; sex ratio 1:1) were obtained from the INERIS husbandry (Verneuil-en-
118 Halatte, France). At the beginning of the experiment, fish were randomly distributed into 8-L tanks with
119 ten fish per tank and a 1:1 sex:ratio (16 ± 1°C, 350 µS/cm, photoperiod of 12:12 h) in a continuous flow
120 system (≈ 1 L/h). Fish were fed daily with frozen blood worms, except the day before they were sampled.
121 After five days of acclimation, fish were exposed for seven days to BPA (99% purity, 0, 10, and 100
122 µg/L, CAS number 80-05-7, Sigma). Water was randomly sampled several times (at 2, 4, 8, 24, 48, 72,
123 and 168 hours) and analyzed with LC-MS/MS (previously described in Mit et al. (2022)). During
124 exposure, all the fish from two tank for each condition, *i.e.*, 20 fish (ten females and ten males) were
125 sampled at 5, 24, 48, 96 and 168 hours. After the end of the exposure, the remaining fish were sampled
126 at 24 hours and 168 hours (192 and 336 hours since the beginning of the experiment, respectively). At
127 each sampling time, fish were anaesthetized (tricaine methanesulfonate, 100 mg/L, Sigma), sacrificed,
128 measured, weighed. The blood, the liver and the carcass were used to measure BPA and BPA metabolite
129 concentrations; spleens were collected to measure immunomarkers.

130 **2.1.2. Long-exposure experiment (21-day)**

131 After five days of acclimation, adult (*i.e.* mature gonads) but sexually inactive sticklebacks with the
132 same life history (similar age, $n = 140$, 52.7 ± 5.6 mm, 1.8 ± 0.6 g, sex ratio 1:1) were exposed for 21
133 days at 0 and 100 µg/L of BPA (nominal concentration). At the beginning of the experiment, males and
134 females were separated to avoid stress and were randomly distributed into 8-L tanks with ten fish per
135 tank and a 1:1 sex:ratio (16 ± 1°C, 350 µS/cm, photoperiod of 12:12 h) in a continuous flow system (≈
136 1 L/h). Fish were fed daily with frozen blood worms, except the day before they were sampled. Water
137 samples were taken from the tanks at 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 days and BPA level was analytically measured.
138 At 7, 14 and 21 days of exposure, all the fish of two tanks for each condition, *i.e.*, 20 fish (ten females
139 and ten males) were sampled. Fish were anaesthetized (tricaine methanesulfonate, 100 mg/L, Sigma),
140 sacrificed, measured, weighed and spleens were collected to measure immunomarkers.

141 **2.1.3. Innate immune biomarker analysis**

142 As previously described by Bado-Nilles et al. (2014), each spleen was pressed through sterilized nylon
143 mesh (40 µm, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) with Leibovitz 15 medium (L15, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) completed
144 with heparin lithium (100 mg/L, Sigma-Aldrich, USA), penicillin (500 mg/L, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and
145 streptomycin (500 mg/L, Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The leucocyte suspension was stored at 4°C for 18 h
146 before analysis to prevent bias due to grinding stress. Measurements were performed on whole
147 leucocytes using a MacsquantX flow cytometer (Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch Gladbach, Germany). To
148 allow comparison between each sample, the leucocyte concentration was normalized to 10⁶ cells/ mL
149 of culture medium.

150 A complete description of the protocols used to measure by flow cytometry the different
151 immunomarkers can be found in Marchand et al. (2017) and Catteau et al. (2019). In the present work,

152 we measured the leucocyte distribution (lymphocyte and granulocyte-macrophage percentages), the
 153 cellular mortality (apoptotic and necrotic cell percentages), the phagocytosis activity (phagocytic
 154 capacity and efficiency, lysosomal presence (Mean Fluorescent Intensity, MFI) and leucocyte
 155 respiratory burst index (ratio of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate stimulated cells over unstimulated cells,
 156 the latter being also denominated as inactivated reactive oxygen species level). A complete description
 157 of the different immune protocols used is provided in supplementary information (SI).

158 2.2. Model structure

159 2.2.1. General structure

160 The model structure of the PBTK-TD (Figure 1) was derived from the PBTK described in Mit et al.
 161 (2022). Briefly, this PBTK was adapted to take into account BPA ADME processes. BPA absorption
 162 was assumed to occur exclusively through the gills and to be distributed via the plasma in 12 well-mixed
 163 compartments. Metabolization was considered as the main process of excretion and to occur in both
 164 liver and venous plasma. Remaining BPA was assumed to be excreted through the gills. The two
 165 predominant metabolic conjugates, BPA glucuronide (BPA gluc) and BPA sulfate (BPA sulf), were then
 166 distributed in five well-mixed compartments. BPA metabolite excretion was assumed to occur only
 167 through the bile.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the physiologically based kinetic model coupled to the toxicodynamics of bisphenol A. Uptake by the gills is symbolized in blue. Metabolization occurs in the liver and in venous plasma (purple). Excretion by the gills and the feces *via* the bile is symbolized

in green. The toxicodynamics of BPA are implemented in the compartments where effects are measured.

168 2.2.2.TD sub-models

169 As innate immune parameters were measured in spleen, the different TD sub-models were implemented
170 in the richly perfused (RP) compartment. Indeed, it was considered to be the compartment with the
171 plasma flow the closest to the spleen. Alternatively, arterial plasma concentration was tested as a proxy
172 for the spleen concentration.

173 A specific class of basic indirect response models was chosen to simulate immunomarkers over time
174 (formally described by Dayneka et al. (1993)). Indeed, contrary to direct responses which are directly
175 affected by a chemical, indirect responses show a lag time after the interaction of the chemical at the
176 site of action. This type of mechanistic model was recommended to describe a response modulation
177 (loss or stimulation) depending on a chemical-receptor interaction (Felmlee et al., 2012).

$$178 \quad \frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} - K_{out} \times R \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

179 Equation 1 describes the measured response R in normal conditions. K_{in} corresponds to a zero-order
180 production rate of the response variable and K_{out} to a first-order rate of the loss of the response. In
181 exposed conditions, a stimulation (Equation 2) or an inhibition (Equation 3) can modulate one of the
182 two rates (Dayneka et al., 1993) (*i.e.*, multiplication of the rate by S(t) or I(t)).

$$183 \quad S(t) = 1 + \frac{S_{max} \times C_{i,t}}{SC_{50} + C_{i,t}} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

$$184 \quad I(t) = 1 - \frac{C_{i,t}}{C_{i,t} + IC_{50}} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

185 With S(t) a stimulation function and I(t) an inhibitory function. $C_i(t)$ represents the concentration in the
186 tissue *i* (alternatively in RP, C_{rp} or in plasma C_p) at the time t. S_{max} the maximum effect attributed to
187 the chemical, SC_{50} the chemical concentration producing 50% of the maximum stimulation and IC_{50}
188 the chemical concentration producing 50% of maximum inhibition.

189 Regarding a potential phenomenon of hysteresis between internal concentration variations and measured
190 response modulations, an additional modification was proposed based on the work of Sheiner et al.
191 (1979). Thus, a better description of the response could be achieved by replacing C_i in Eq.2 or Eq.3 with
192 the concentration corresponding to a virtual compartment *D* to account for the observed delay (see
193 Equation 4).

$$194 \quad \frac{dD_i}{dt} = k_{delay} \times (C_i - D_i) \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

195 With k_{delay} a dimensionless constant. Finally, to take into account a potential loop regulation of the
196 measured response during the exposure, a feedback sub-model was implemented based on the work of

197 Bundgaard et al. (2007). Depending on the measured response, a modulation variable was added to
198 suppress the stimulation or inhibition of the response at a given time.

$$199 \quad M = (t - \tau) \times k_{tol} \quad \text{(Equation 5)}$$

200 With M the modulator, t the time, τ the time at which the feedback starts and k_{tol} a modulatory constant.

201 The equation 6 is given as an example of a model integrating a modulator and a virtual compartment for
202 a production stimulated response with D_{rp} being the damage produced by the concentration of chemical
203 in the richly perfused tissue.

$$204 \quad \frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{S_{max} \times D_{rp}}{SC_{50} + D_{rp}} \right) \times \frac{1}{M} - K_{out} \times R \quad \text{(Equation 6)}$$

205 **2.3. Biomarker response analysis and modeling**

206 Calculations were performed using R version 3.6.1. (R Core Team, 2019) and GNU MCSim v6.2.0
207 (Bois, 2009). MCSim model codes were provided in SI (section 7).

208 **2.3.1. Statistical analysis**

209 Prior to modelling, a statistical analysis was performed for each immunomarker response. All responses
210 were log-transformed. At each date, a one-way ANOVA followed by a post-hoc Dunnett test was used
211 to detect significant differences between treated conditions and control. The level of significance for all
212 the analysis was 5%. The biomarkers presenting the most consistent differences to control over time
213 (*i.e.*, the dose-response was repeatedly observed during the exposure period) were then selected for the
214 PBTK-TD modelling. Detailed statistical analysis for each endpoint is presented in SI (section 5).

215 **2.3.2. Calibration of the biomarker responses**

216 Based on the results of the statistical analysis, a combination of the TD sub-models was used to describe
217 each selected biomarker response. For the calibration, all TK parameters were fixed and only TD
218 parameters were calibrated (seven parameters for inactivated ROS and eight parameters for lysosomal
219 presence and phagocytic efficiency). Most prior distributions were set as normal, and the coefficient of
220 variation on the prior values was set to 30 % (including uncertainty and inter-individual variability).
221 Mean prior values were retrieved from Marchand et al. (2019).

222 TD data corresponding to both short and long-exposure period were used to inform parameter posterior
223 values. Prior to the calibration of the parameters using BPA TD data, control data were used to calibrate
224 the baseline level of each response. TD models were calibrated on the geometric means of male and
225 female altogether with the same weight for males and females. As described in Mit et al. (2022), BPA
226 concentration levels in water that were used as input for the PBPK model were based on the measured
227 concentrations. Other model inputs like initial fish weight and water temperature were set to the values

228 obtained by monitoring both experiments. Calibration was performed using Bayesian methods (Monte
229 Carlo Markov Chains, MCMC). See all details in SI (section 6).

230 **2.3.3. Comparison of the models**

231 To determine which chemical, parent or metabolites, could be responsible for the measured responses,
232 six versions of the model describing each biomarker were calibrated. In each model, one of the three
233 simulated concentrations in RP compartment and arterial plasma (BPA, BPA gluc or BPA sulf) was
234 used as input in the TD sub-model. In addition, the various models were calibrated on the observed ratio
235 of the biomarker response in treated conditions over the control. Afterwards, Bayesian Inference Criteria
236 (BIC), measuring goodness of fit and allowing the comparison of the different models, were calculated.

237 **3. Results**

238 In control aquarium, BPA and metabolites were below the detection limit (Table SI3). Measured BPA
239 concentrations in water in the short experience were $5.0 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $53.0 \pm 19.3 \mu\text{g/L}$ (mean \pm SD,
240 nominal concentrations of 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$). During the long-exposure experiment, fish were exposed
241 to $55.9 \pm 6.3 \mu\text{g/L}$ (nominal concentration level 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$).

242 **3.1. Innate immune parameter analysis**

243 A total of nine immunomarkers was measured during the two experiments. No significant difference
244 was observed between male and female for any measured parameters (see section 5 in SI).

245 **3.1.1. Leucocyte distribution**

246 Even if the percentages of granulocytes-macrophages tend to decrease throughout the experiment, only
247 the highest dose at 0.25 day of exposure and the two doses on day 14 were significant. No significant
248 response was found for the 21-day exposure (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Leucocyte distribution (percentage of granulocytes and macrophages on leucocyte population) of three-spined stickleback during the short-exposure (left panel) and the long-exposure (right panel) experiments. *Asterisks* mark to statistically significant differences between control (blank) and treated conditions (10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of BPA in light purple and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of BPA in purple, $n = 20$).

249 **3.1.2. Cellular mortality**

250 Regarding cellular mortality, two parameters were measured, apoptotic and necrotic cell percentages
251 (Figure 3). At the highest dose level (100 $\mu\text{g/L}$) a significantly higher percentage of cellular mortality
252 (sum of apoptosis and necrosis percentages) was observed on day 1 in the short-exposure experiment
253 (see SI section 5.2). No significant effect was observed during the depuration phase. In addition, no
254 significant effect was observed during the 21-day experiment (Figure 3 right panel).

Figure 3. Cellular mortality (apoptosis and necrosis) of three-spined stickleback during the short-exposure (left panel) and the long-exposure (right panel) experiments. *Asterisks* mark to statistically significant differences between control (blank) and treated conditions (10 µg/L of BPA in light purple and 100 µg/L of BPA in purple, $n = 20$).

255 **3.1.3. Phagocytic activity**

256 Phagocytic activity concerned the attachment of the cell to foreign particles (phagocytic capacity), the
 257 internalization of the particle (phagocytic efficiency) (Figure 4), the lysosomal presence (Figure 5) and
 258 the respiratory burst (Figure 6). Overall, each parameter of phagocytic activity in exposed fish tends to
 259 increase compared to control fish. In fact, a significant induction in phagocytic capacity was measured
 260 on day 1 and day 8 for 100 µg/L for the short exposure (Figure 4A). This effect of induction was also
 261 found to be significant on day 7 for the 21-day exposure (Figure 4B). In terms of phagocytic efficiency,
 262 a significant induction was observed on day 1, 7 and 8 for the highest dose for the short exposure (Figure
 263 4C) and also on day 7 for the 21-day exposure (Figure 4D).

Figure 4. Splenic immune phagocytosis capacity (upper line) and efficiency (lower line) of three-spined stickleback during the short-exposure (right panel, A and C) and the long-exposure (left panel, B and D) experiments. *Asterisks* mark to statistically significant differences between control (blank) and treated conditions (10 µg/L of BPA in light purple and 100 µg/L of BPA in purple, $n = 20$).

264 During the short-exposure, an induction of lysosomal presence was significant on day 0.25 for both
 265 doses and the induction was also significant on day 1, 4 and 7 for the highest dose (Figure 5). During
 266 the depuration phase, this biomarker was significantly induced at both doses on day 8 and still induced
 267 on day 14 at the highest dose level (Figure 5). In the 21-day experiment, no significant effect was
 268 observed (Figure 5 right panel).

Figure 5. Splenic lysosomal presence during the short-exposure (left panel) and the long-exposure (right panel) experiments. *Asterisks* mark statistically significant differences between control (blank) and treated conditions (10 µg/L of BPA in light purple and 100 µg/L of BPA in purple, $n = 20$).

269 A significant induction of inactivated ROS levels at the two doses was observed on day 1 and only the
 270 highest dose on day 4 (Figure 6A). On day 7, all doses were significantly induced. During the depuration
 271 phase, the induction was significant for the highest dose level on day 8 (Figure 6A). Finally, inactivated
 272 ROS levels were induced at all doses on day 14 (Figure 6A). In the 21-day experiment, ROS B was
 273 significantly induced at all timepoints (Figure 6B).

274 Respiratory burst index (Figure 6C and D) was significantly induced at the highest dose level on day
 275 0.25 and at the dose level 10 µg/L on days 1 and 4. On day 7, respiratory burst was significantly inhibited
 276 at dose level 10 µg/L (Figure 6C). During the depuration phase a significant induction of the respiratory
 277 burst was observed at both dose levels on day 8. For the long exposure, a significant inhibition was
 278 measured on days 7 and 14 (Figure 6D).

Figure 6. Respiratory burst of three-spined stickleback during the short (right-hand column, A and C) and the long (left-hand column, B and D) exposures. *Asterisks* mark statistically significant differences between control (blank) and treated conditions (10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of BPA in light purple and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of BPA in purple, $n = 20$).

279 3.2. Biomarker response modelling

280 Model inputs and parameters can be found in SI (table S11). Figure 7 presents the concentrations of
 281 BPA and BPA gluc predicted by the PBTK (Mit et al., 2022) for the two exposures both in plasma and
 282 richly perfused tissues. In the short experiment, a slower depuration kinetics of BPA glu in plasma (from
 283 day 7) was observed compared to the kinetic of the parent compound. Those predicted tissue
 284 concentrations represent the inputs of the different TD sub-models.

Figure 7. Richly perfused tissue (blue lines) and plasma (red lines) BPA and BPA glu concentrations for the short and long exposure. Full lines represent the BPA and dotted lines BPA glu.

285

286 Among biomarkers, two-responses were selected: the phagocytic efficiency and the inactivated ROS
 287 level. Those biomarkers were chosen based on the consistency (*i.e.*, the dose-response was repeatedly
 288 observed during the exposure period) of their response over time.

289 Table 2 presents the comparison of the BICs calculated for each response using BPA or BPA metabolite
 290 in RP tissues and arterial plasma as model inputs. The lowest BIC was observed when phagocytic
 291 efficiency was modelled with BPA glu concentration in arterial plasma used as an input. Regarding
 292 inactivated ROS modeled responses, the lowest BIC was obtained with BPA concentration in arterial
 293 plasma as input.

Table 2. Comparison of the Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) obtained for the two different modeled immune parameters. Each response was calibrated using the concentrations of BPA and its metabolites in RP tissues or in plasma as input in the toxicodynamic model.

	BPA		BPA glu		BPA sulf.	
	RP Tissues	Plasma	RP Tissues	Plasma	RP Tissues	Plasma
Phagocytic efficiency	-25.2	-28.1	-28.5	-34.1	-23.0	-23.1
Inactivated ROS	47.7	43.4	44.4	45.4	55.4	53.1

294 The phagocytic efficiency and inactivated ROS were induced by BPA or its metabolites. Therefore, the
 295 Equation 2 mimicking a response stimulation was chosen to model each biomarker response (Figure 8,
 296 9 and 10).

Figure 8. Phagocytic internalization efficiency ratio simulated by the PBTK-TD model (Equation 6) based on the BPA glu concentration in arterial plasma for the short and long exposure. The solid lines represent the model simulations and the dots the ratio (treated conditions over controls) of the

response. The grey area is the 95% credibility interval computed from the posterior distributions. The simulations were made using the last 333 iterations of the three MCMC chains. Error bars represent the standard deviation on the observed ratios.

297

Figure 9. Phagocytic internalization efficiency ratio simulated by the PBTK-TD model (Equation 7) based on the BPA gluc concentration in arterial plasma for the short and long exposure. The solid lines represent the model simulations and the dots the ratio (treated conditions over controls) of the response. The grey area is the 95% credibility interval computed from the posterior distributions. The simulations were made using the last 333 iterations of the three MCMC chains. Error bars represent the standard deviation on the observed ratios

298 Phagocytic internalization efficiency was best modelled using BPA gluc concentration in arterial plasma
 299 and a loop regulation.

300 More precisely, model backward selection (Table S12 in SI) showed that the models integrating a virtual
 301 compartment to add a delay (Equation 6, Figure 8) or based directly on the BPA gluc concentration in
 302 arterial plasma (Equation 7, Figure 9) provide similar results, with a slightly lower BIC for the latter.
 303 However, focusing on the end of the exposure, without delay, the response stability observed between
 304 the day 7 and 8 is less accurately modelled.

$$305 \quad \frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{S_{max} \times C_{art\ glu}}{S_{C50} + C_{art\ glu}} \right) \times \frac{1}{M} - K_{out} \times R \quad \text{(Equation 7)}$$

306 Once calibrated, both TD model provide accurate predictions with a mean fold equal to 1.079 and 1.076,
 307 respectively. The predicted phagocytic internalization efficiency at nominal dose level 10 µg/L showed
 308 a mean induction of 15% compared to control (Figure 8 and 9). 73% of the observed points were within
 309 the 95% prediction interval. However, phagocytic internalization efficiency was under-predicted at 14
 310 days, highlighting a high observed level of induction even after seven days of depuration. Both in the
 311 short-exposure and the long-exposure experiments at nominal dose level 100 µg/L, the predicted

312 induction in treated conditions was around 25% greater than the control. The data were correctly fitted,
 313 including the 14-day point during the depuration. However, comparing the point measured on day 7 at
 314 nominal dose level 100 µg/L in the short and long-exposure experiment (Figure 7) with the plateau
 315 simulated by the model, it reveals an underprediction of the model, and a quite good reproducibility of
 316 the induction between the two experiments. Model calibration seems to have led to a tradeoff between
 317 the accuracy in low and high dose at this time point. Finally, the loop regulation integrated in our model
 318 (Eq.5) correctly fitted the return to the baseline between day 7 and day 21.

319 Regarding inactivated ROS, Equation 4 was simplified so that no depuration occurred in the virtual
 320 compartment (Equation 8) and no loop regulation was introduced (see Equation 9).

321
$$\frac{dD_{rp}}{dt} = k_{delay} \times C_{rp} \quad \text{(Equation 8)}$$

322
$$\frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{S_{max} \times D_{rp}}{SC_{50} + D_{rp}} \right) - K_{out} \times R \quad \text{(Equation 9)}$$

323

Figure 10. Inactivated ROS level ratio simulated by the PBTK-TD model based on BPA plasma concentration for the short and long exposure. The solid lines represent the model simulations and the dots the ratio (conditions over controls) of the response. The grey area is the 95% prediction interval, computed from the posterior distributions. The simulations were made using the last 333 iterations of the three MCMC chains. Error bars correspond to the standard deviation on the mean ratios.

324 Once calibrated, TD model provide accurate predictions with a mean fold equal to 1.38. The inactivated
 325 ROS response (Figure 10) was quite different and showed a continuous increase during the exposure
 326 period in both experiments. Steady states were reached only after the short exposure, once the exposure
 327 stopped (mean ratio around 25% higher than the control for the 10 µg/L dose level and around 120% at
 328 the 100 µg/L dose level). Consequently, in the 21-day experiment, the mean ratio predicted by the model
 329 reached 300% of the control at 21 days of exposure. Our simulations stressed an important variability
 330 regarding the responses over time. The simple equations included in our model failed to predict the large
 331 increases and decreases between successive timepoints observed during each exposure.

332

333 4. Discussion

334 The present work is part of a continuous effort made in ecotoxicology to improve the characterization
335 of biomarkers. In Forbes et al. (2006), the use and limitations of those tools was discussed. Among the
336 main concerns on the subject, the difficulty to untangle their biological variability due to confounding
337 factors (sex, season, species...) and the actual effect of xenobiotics was highlighted. One of the solutions
338 proposed in this work was to build mechanism-based models integrating relevant sub-individual
339 parameters. In our paper, toxicodynamic sub-models were implemented in a PBTK specific to BPA. In
340 parallel, two exposures to BPA were performed. One exposure (the short exposure) was described
341 previously in Mit et al., 2022 and the other (the long exposure) was described in this work. The
342 monitoring of immunomarkers in both experiments is presented for the first time in this paper. A
343 selection of the responses measured in fish were then modeled using the PBTK-TD.

344 So far, inconsistent results regarding BPA effects on innate immune parameters were described in the
345 literature (Pandey et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2015). Nevertheless, in line with other research, the present
346 study demonstrated the immunomodulatory potential of BPA. Here, we showed that phagocytic activity
347 of splenic leukocytes taken from fish exposed to BPA was induced following a dose dependent
348 relationship and this effect was measurable quickly after the beginning of the exposure. In Yang et al.
349 (2015), this induction was also observed in trout head kidney macrophages exposed *in vitro* during 6 h
350 to 1 and 10 µg/L of BPA. Interestingly, in Yang et al. (2015) at higher doses, phagocytic activity was
351 significantly inhibited showing a non-monotonic dose response (NMDR). On the contrary, in *Channa*
352 *punctatus*, another teleost fish, the phagocytic activity was significantly inhibited *in vitro* after 16 h of
353 exposure even at low dose (from 0.229 µg/L to 229 µg/L) (Pandey et al., 2018).

354 In the current study, both phagocytosis capacity and efficiency, lysosomal presence and respiratory burst
355 were also measured. The lysosomal presence was significantly induced but the respiratory burst dynamic
356 was not monotonic over time. Depending on the studies, the respiratory burst was reported to be induced
357 (Faheem and Bhandari, 2021; Samuel et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2015) or inhibited (Bado-Nilles et al.,
358 2014; Yin et al., 2007). In fact, BPA was shown to modulate various genes associated to the NF-κB
359 signalling pathway. BPA up-regulates pro-inflammatory cytokine genes such as Tumor Necrosis Factor
360 α (*tnf- α*), involved in the enhancing response of phagocyte respiratory burst (Faheem et al., 2020;
361 Faheem and Bhandari, 2021). On the contrary, at higher dose, BPA immunosuppression was
362 demonstrated in various species, including *Gobiocypris rarus* and *Labeo rohita* larvae (Faheem et al.,
363 2020; Tao et al., 2016). Some hypotheses could be proposed to explain those contradictory results. As
364 it was highlighted previously, it is generally assumed that the immunomarker dynamic is stable over
365 time, but it was shown here that it depends on the biomarker considered. Another hypothesis could be a
366 differential expression of estrogen receptor α and β depending on tissue type resulting in discrepancies
367 in response measured in splenic or head kidney macrophages (Bado-Nilles et al., 2014; Filby and Tyler,
368 2005). Indeed, leucocytes and, in particular, macrophages possess estrogen receptors (ERs) (Casanova-

369 Nakayama et al., 2011; Massart et al., 2014) and NF- κ B and ERs were linked to the immunomodulating
370 effect of BPA (Yang et al., 2015).

371 The PBTK specific to BPA and calibrated on TK data measured in three-spined stickleback used in this
372 study was presented in a previous work (Mit et al., 2022). While PBTK are often used as a basis when
373 studying effects in toxicology, the approach presented here is still scarce in ecotoxicology (Abbas and
374 Hayton, 1997; Liao et al., 2005; Ling et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2014; Mit et al., 2021; Tebby et al., 2019;
375 Zhang et al., 2019). Yet, PBTK models offer many advantages compared to simpler TK model, in
376 particular, when considering effects at the sub-individual level, the predictions of internal concentrations
377 in target organs could improve greatly the accuracy of the modeled response (Grech et al., 2017; Mit et
378 al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2019). In addition, contrary to most dose-response studies which used static
379 model, our study describes the response over time. In terms of effect, most of studies in the field of
380 ecotoxicology are focusing on three endpoints, namely survival, reproduction, and growth. However,
381 the impacts at the individual level can be considered as late effects when applying to biomonitoring or
382 to the evaluation of substances inducing non-directly lethal effects, like EDCs. In this context, the
383 development of models integrating early responses, like PBTK-TD, are needed. Moreover, our work
384 coupling experimental and modelling approaches enabled to highlight the discrepancy of some
385 datapoints that could be mistaken for an actual particular response whereas it is probably an artifact due
386 to experimental issues. For example, the measured phagocytic efficiency on day 4 for both doses for the
387 short-exposure experiment sounds incoherent with the mechanisms assumed by model and supported
388 by the other datapoints.

389 Only few models have integrated biomarker responses in ecotoxicology, the first one being the PBTK-
390 TD developed by Abbas and Hayton (1997) and describing the inhibition of AChE by chlorpyrifos in
391 rainbow trout. In this model, the response was a consequence of the dynamic of enzyme synthesis,
392 degradation, and inhibition. In our case, the mechanisms underlying the immunomarker responses were
393 unknown. For this reason, a class of indirect toxicodynamic models was chosen (Dayneka et al., 1993).
394 Nevertheless, the dynamics that were observed when measuring immunomarkers over time showed the
395 limitations of those indirect models. As it is often observed in the literature, there was a discrepancy
396 between the internal concentration and the response (Lee et al., 2002). However, even if the measured
397 responses were sometimes slow to dissipate, most responses were quickly triggered. It was for example
398 the case for the phagocytosis activity. In this respect, indirect models were unable to correctly simulate
399 this dynamic. In addition, the implementation of the virtual compartment based on the work of Sheiner
400 et al. (1979) was insufficient to perfectly fit the measured data since the modeled responses were
401 triggered too slowly. The simulations showed that the best model was probably a trade-off between a
402 basic indirect model and its updated version including the virtual compartment. Another process
403 highlighted by our PBPK-TD modeling approach was the feedback phenomenon measured in the long
404 exposure for some markers. For this reason and according to Bundgaard et al. (2007), the return to the

405 basal value under exposure was introduced in the TD model. The mechanism underlying this dynamic
406 is unclear. However, it is possible that in the absence of actual infection, the organism is able to modulate
407 the response triggered by BPA to prevent energy waste. Nevertheless, for other responses like the
408 production of ROS involved in the destruction of pathogens, the mechanism dynamic seems to be
409 controlled by another mechanism.

410 One key issue during the development of a PBTK-TD is the amount of data needed to inform both the
411 TK and the TD of the substance of interest. In Mit et al. (2022), the levels of BPA and BPA metabolites
412 were measured in three organs, at several times and for two doses. The design of this study, including
413 uptake and depuration, was chosen to inform ADME parameters. Considering the toxicodynamic part
414 presented here, two experiments were performed. The first one with a 7-day exposure followed by a 7-
415 day depuration (same experiment for TK) was selected to evaluate the earliness of the response and its
416 potential return to basal value after exposure. The second one, the long-exposure experiment, was
417 selected to determine how the biomarkers of interest would evolve over a longer period. As it can be
418 noticed with our selection of immunomarkers, the dynamic of the responses were heterogenous.
419 Notably, biomarkers describing phagocytosis showed the importance of conducting the most complete
420 study when measuring biomarker dynamic. Thus, non-monotonic responses over time can be identified
421 as it was the case for phagocytosis efficiency or lysosomal presence. Regarding dose-response, only a
422 selection of several doses, over a sufficiently large range of concentrations, would allow the
423 identification of potential non-monotonic dose responses (Beausoleil et al., 2013; Vandenberg et al.,
424 2012). In our case, fish were exposed to two doses of BPA (plus the control). Given the limited number
425 of concentrations, it was not possible to conclude about the shape of the dose-dependency of the different
426 responses, even if some inducted or inhibited responses were highlighted over the small range of tested
427 concentrations. In fact, in Beausoleil et al. (2013), BPA, as most of EDCs, was characterized by NMDR
428 for a variety of effects. Considering our results, it is interesting to note that the existence of a feedback
429 phenomenon or a potential desensitization of a receptor could be mistakenly interpreted as for a dose
430 dependency whereas the measured response appears to be unstable over time (Beausoleil et al., 2013).

431 For each immunomarker, one of the three simulated concentrations in RP compartment and arterial
432 plasma (BPA, BPA gluc or BPA sulf) was used as input in the TD sub-model. The lowest BIC was
433 observed regarding inactivated ROS with BPA concentration in arterial plasma as input, whereas the
434 BPA gluc concentration in arterial plasma provides the lowest BIC regarding phagocytic efficiency. In
435 human, one recent experimental work has examined the in vitro effects of BPA and BPA gluc on
436 glycolysis and functional responses of neutrophils (Peillex et al., 2021). Contrary to our results, the
437 authors found no effect of BPA nor BPA gluc on phagocytosis and ROS production. Nevertheless, BPA
438 gluc was identified as a potentially higher disruptor than its parent. Furthermore, in this work, the short
439 timeframe of the experiment and an extensive literature regarding the immunotoxic effects of BPA was
440 stressed to balance the conclusion about the absence of effect of BPA gluc. In lines with the disrupting

441 potential of BPA gluc, Boucher et al. (2015) showed the potential of the metabolite to induce
442 adipogenesis in both murine and human cells.

443 Mixture of the parent compound and the metabolites could be also assumed to be responsible for the
444 toxic effect. This assumption could be tested using the PBTK-TD model to predict dose-response curves
445 for equitoxic mixtures where each chemical contributes equally to the total toxicity (Mit et al. 2021).
446 However, an equitoxic mixture seems a bit speculative, and more data have to be obtained on the toxicity
447 of the isolated metabolites to explore some possible interactions. Nevertheless, it is important to note
448 that if the effect is better explained by the concentration of one of the substances, this does not exclude
449 a lesser effect of the other and thus a combined effect of the mixture.

450 Currently, biomarkers are used in environmental biomonitoring to assess the health of aquatic
451 ecosystems (Catteau et al., 2021; Catteau et al., 2022). Following the different points highlighted by
452 Forbes et al. (2006), a continuous work was performed to reduce the uncertainty induced by the
453 confounding factors complicating the use of biomarkers. In our work, the focus was made on the
454 temporal dynamic of the biomarkers. The variety of biomarker temporal dynamic obtained under the
455 same exposure conditions stressed the need to study the impact of time on biomarkers measure as
456 frequently as it is for the dose-response. Indeed, the characterization of the time-dependency and
457 knowledge of the variability of the response between biomarkers provide opportunity to propose various
458 hypothesis regarding the mechanisms underlying the different responses. For example, comparing stable
459 and unstable biomarker responses over time (*e.g.* inactivated ROS and phagocytic efficiency) can
460 provide information on the dynamics of the underlying stress.

461 In addition to a better understanding of the dynamics of innate immune parameters currently used in
462 biomonitoring (Bado-Nilles et al., 2014; Catteau et al., 2021), the integration of those responses in a
463 PBTK-TD will benefit the current effort of bringing together existing data to support ecotoxicological
464 risk assessment in building quantitative adverse outcome pathways (Ankley et al., 2010; David et al.,
465 2019). In this work, the modulation of immune parameters was not linked to any notable detrimental
466 effects affecting three-spined stickleback. However, the triggering of innate immune defence, as
467 observed here, is energetically costly (Pandey et al., 2018) and could result in a trade-off with other
468 biological functions. However, in Spromberg and Meador (2006), the modeling of immune suppression
469 resulting from an exposure to low dose of toxicants was supposed to only impact the ability to resist to
470 pathogens and therefore to impact survival. Conversely, in stickleback, it was shown that the infection
471 resistant offsprings resulting from the mating of brightly colored male were growing slowly supporting
472 the idea of trade-offs between growth and immunity (Barber et al., 2001). Finally, the proven
473 bidirectional communication between immunity and neuroendocrine systems taken with the known
474 disturbance of immune responses during reproduction support the idea of trade-off between
475 reproduction and immunity (Bado-Nilles et al., 2014; Casanova-Nakayama et al., 2011). To predict the
476 potential effect of biomarker modulation on the population of fish, future work should focus on

477 quantifying those trade-offs, for example by measuring *in vivo* or by searching in the literature the effect
478 of varying immunocompetence in fish on the different biological functions.

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487 Writing - Review & Editing.
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494

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